

PREPARATION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF METAL/SiO₂ NANOCOMPOSITE AEROGELS

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SUMMARY: Metal-containing tetraethyl orthosilicate (M-TEOS) serve as the sol-gel precursors to prepare the Metal/SiO₂ nanocomposite aerogels of high metal content. The good dispersion and interfacial properties of nanophase metal particles on silica aerogels are formed by the sol-gel processing of M-TEOS, oxidation and reduce process at high temperature. The oxidating and reducing temperature have a heavy effect on the specific surface area of nanocomposite aerogel. BET result shows that metal (Fe, Co or Ni)/SiO₂ nanocomposite aerogels have high specific surface area (400~700m²/g). The particles size of the Metal/SiO₂ nanocomposite aerogel are mostly in the range of 5~25nm by (SAXS).

Key words: sol-gel processing, nanocomposite aerogel, supercritical drying, Ni-containing TEOS, TEOS

INTRODUCTION

The sol-gel polymerization of metal alkoxides allows the formation of numerous nanoscale ceramic oxide materials^[1]. That exhibit technologically important optical, mechanical and electrical properties^[2]. Nanocomposite aerogels consisting of very small particles (typically nanoscale particles having diameters less than 100 nm) of a guest substance dispersed throughout a host matrix are a topic of intense current interest for potential applications in ionic conductor, chemical sensors or catalysts and as magnetic, electronic, or photonic (nonlinear optical) materials^[3,4]. Guest substances of metals are of particular interest for these applications.

In general, nanocomposite aerogels containing nanoscale metals dispersed in a silica aerogel host matrix may be prepared by impregnating the silica aerogel with an appropriate metal salt solution, and drying the gels at elevated temperatures in air and then reducing the oxide particles, but nanocomposite aerogels made has low specific surface area, or by doping metal salts into conventional sol-gel synthesis of silica aerogel followed by oxidative and reductive thermal treatments, but metal content of nanocomposite aerogels prepared are low owing to the most metal in the gels escape from the gels in the solvent exchange and the supercritical drying process. In this paper, M-TEOS are applied to prepare the metal/SiO₂ nanocomposite aerogels of high metal content.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Metal-containing TEOS (M-TEOS) have been prepared by reacting tetraethoxysilane (TEOS) with a transition metal salts in the present of catalyst. The Metal-containing TEOS or the mixtures of Metal-containing TEOS and TEOS are used as precursors. Typically, 45 ml of Metal-containing TEOS were stirred with 20 ml of ethanol (EtOH). 15 ml of H₂O containing a few drops of concentrated HCl was then added to this solution (molar ratios of M-TEOS:EtOH:H₂O are =1:4:10) which was warmed with stirring at ~50°C for 2 h. The coloured sol was then transferred to glass test tube and placed in a 70°C thermautostat, where gelation occurred after a few days.

To form aerogels, the solvent was removed from the wet alcogels by supercritical drying of ethanol. Aerogels were oxidated in air at 400°C to break the covalent linkage between metal and silica aerogel, and then reduced in hydrogen at 400°C to produce Metal/SiO₂ Nanocomposite Aerogels.

The content of metal in the nanocomposite aerogels is measured by chemical analysis. The size of Ni particles in the catalyst and its distribution were determined by means of the small-angle X-ray scattering (SAXS) technique. The specific surface area of the metal/SiO₂ nanocomposite aerogels were determined by using BET-adsorption/desorption technique.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Metal-containing tetraethoxysilane (M-TEOS) is prepared by attaching a transition metal via a chemical covalent linkage to tetraethoxysilane(TEOS). These molecules (M-TEOS) serve as the sol-gel precursors. Addition of these molecules to a conventional sol-gel recipe leads to hydrolysis and condensation of the silicate ester functional groups with the resulting silica aerogel matrix by the supercritical drying of ethanol. This chemical linkage between metal and silica aerogel matrix apparently gives more uniform dispersion of the metal throughout the aerogel. Subsequent oxidative and reductive thermal treatments results in metal/SiO₂ nanocomposite aerogels containing nanoscale metals. The metal/SiO₂ nanocomposite aerogels very small metal and SiO₂ particles with narrow size distributions. Selected nanoscale metal particles in metal/SiO₂ nanocomposite aerogels of the following metals have been prepared by using this method: Fe, Co, Ni.

In the conventional preparation of metal/SiO₂ nanocomposite aerogels, addition of metals is directly doping metal salts into sol-gel precursors solution. In the following process of the solvent exchange and the supercritical drying, metal ion might escape from gels. Consequently, the metal/SiO₂ nanocomposite aerogels is low content of metals, e.g. the content of metal in the metal/SiO₂ nanocomposite aerogels is less than 0.5wt%^[5]. However, the rate of metal retention in the metal/SiO₂ nanocomposite aerogels prepared by sol-gel process of metal-containing tetraethoxysilane (M-TEOS) is approximately 90%, the highest metal content could reach 60wt%^[6], shown in Table 1. It is quite apparent that the metal in the gels can't escape from the gels because of metal attaching to tetraethoxysilane(TEOS) via a chemical covalent linkage.

Table 1 Ni/Si molar ratio in the feed and Ni/SiO₂ nanocomposite aerogel and the rate of Ni retention

Ni/Si in the feed	0.097	0.151	0.250	0.368	0.575
Ni/Si in Ni/SiO ₂ aerogel	0.088	0.140	0.219	0.316	0.490
the rate of Ni retention(wt%)	91.5	93.6	89.8	89.3	90.1

*(NiTEOS+TEOS)/C₂H₅OH/H₂O=1:4:10(molar ratio). [HCl]=0.05M

The temperature of oxidating and reducing aerogels have a heavy effect on the specific surface area of the metal/SiO₂ nanocomposite aerogels. In the course of oxidating and reducing aerogels, the chemical linkage between metal and silica aerogel matrix are completely broken and the microstructure of silica aerogel matrix are partly destroyed. That the deposition of metal on the silica aerogel and the microstructure of aerogels are partly destroyed results in the decrease of the specific surface area of the metal/SiO₂ nanocomposite aerogels. The specific surface area of Ni/SiO₂ nanocomposite aerogels in which the Ni weight percentage is 15.2% decrease with the increase of oxidating and reducing temperature (Figure 1). It is because that the higher oxidating temperature could more heavily destroy the microstructure of Ni/SiO₂ nanocomposite aerogels. It is also found that the specific surface area of metal//SiO₂ nanocomposite aerogels decreases with increasing the time of thermal treatment.

Fig.1 The effect of oxidating and reducing temperature on the specific surface area of Ni/SiO₂ nanocomposite aerogels

Experiments results of BET of Ni/SiO₂ nanocomposite aerogels showed that the specific surface areas of Ni/SiO₂ nanocomposite aerogels are as high as 400~700m²/g,. It is also found that the surface areas of Ni/SiO₂ nanocomposite aerogels decrease as metal content increases, as listed in Table 2. It is apparent that the break of the chemical linkage between metal and silica aerogel in the course of thermal treatments of metal/SiO₂ nanocomposite aerogels destroys the structure of the nanocomposite aerogels, and results in the decrease of surface area of metal/SiO₂ nanocomposite aerogels. The variation of the specific surface areas of Fe/SiO₂ and Co/SiO₂ nanocomposite aerogels with the increase of metal content are similar to those of the specific surface area of Ni/SiO₂ nanocomposite aerogels.

Table 2: Surface areas of metal/SiO₂ nanocomposite aerogels

Fe/SiO ₂ aerogels	Content of Fe (wt%)	7.1	10.9	16.8	21.5	28.8
	Surface areas (m ² /g)	594.2	522.4	411.3	403.9	400.2
Ni/SiO ₂ aerogels	Content of Ni (wt%)	8.1	12.3	18.0	24.0	32.9
	Surface areas(m ² /g)	648.1	574.0	440.9	439.3	426.5
Co/SiO ₂ aerogels	Content of Co (wt%)	7.8	11.7	18.2	23.6	31.8
	Surface areas(m ² /g)	694.8	620.2	485.3	472.5	464.2

The metal/SiO₂ nanocomposite aerogel prepared above have very small metal and SiO₂ particles with narrow size distributions. That the metal particle and SiO₂ particles are respectively determined is difficult. The SAXS^[7] result of Ni/SiO₂ nanocomposite aerogels showed that Ni/SiO₂ nanocomposite aerogel particles size (Ni:16.1wt%) are mostly in the range of 5~25nm, the mean particle diameter is 15.9nm, and the weight percentage of particles less than 10nm is 70.9%, as shown in Fig. 2. The particles size distribution of Fe/SiO₂ and Co/SiO₂ nanocomposite aerogels are similar to those of Ni/SiO₂ nanocomposite aerogel.

Fig. 2 Relationship of particle size and weight percentage of Ni/SiO₂ aerogel (detected by SAXS)

CONCLUSION

Our method for the preparation of very small and highly dispersed metals on SiO₂ aerogels particles with narrow size distributions, e.g., metal/SiO₂ nanocomposite aerogels, by using metal-containing tetraethoxysilane (M-TEOS) as the sol-gel precursors during sol-gel processing, appears to be very effective. It can also be applied to control the metal particle size distribution in bimetallic SiO₂ nanocomposite aerogels.

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